

TECHNICAL REPORT

Implementation and Configuration of Open-Source 5G Core Network Using free5GC and UERANSIM:

A Practical Deployment Guide with Troubleshooting

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Abstract

This technical report documents practical implementation experience with free5GC open-source 5G core network as part of doctoral research in 5G networking at Nanjing University of Information Science and Technology. The deployment of 5G networks has become a critical area of research and development in telecommunications, and open-source implementations provide accessible platforms for experimentation.

This guide presents a comprehensive methodology for deploying free5GC along with UERANSIM simulator on Ubuntu 20.04 LTS, including system configuration, network setup, and component integration. The report emphasizes practical challenges encountered during deployment - such as dependency conflicts, network configuration issues, and integration problems - and provides tested solutions.

Successful establishment of PDU sessions and internet connectivity validates the deployment approach. This work serves as both a practical reference for establishing 5G testbeds and a contribution of hands-on implementation knowledge to the research community.

Keywords: 5G Core Network, free5GC, UERANSIM, Open-Source 5G, Network Function Virtualization, 3GPP, Service-Based Architecture

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background

Fifth-generation (5G) mobile networks represent a significant evolution in telecommunications technology, offering enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB), ultra-reliable low-latency communications (URLLC), and massive machine-type communications (mMTC). The 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) has standardized the 5G system architecture, introducing a Service-Based Architecture (SBA) for the core network that leverages cloud-native principles and enables flexible deployment scenarios (1).

The development and testing of 5G applications and services require access to 5G infrastructure, which can be prohibitively expensive for academic institutions and individual researchers. Open-source implementations of the 5G core network have emerged as valuable tools for education, research, and prototyping. Among these, free5GC has gained significant attention as a comprehensive, standards-compliant implementation of the 5G core network (2).

1.2 Motivation

While comprehensive documentation exists for free5GC installation, practical deployment often reveals undocumented challenges including dependency conflicts and network configuration issues. Motivated by enthusiasm for 5G technology and hands-on experimentation, this guide provides a tested deployment methodology that addresses these practical implementation hurdles.

1.3 Objectives

The primary objectives of this technical report are:

1. To document a complete, reproducible deployment procedure for free5GC and UERANSIM
2. To identify and document common implementation challenges with their solutions
3. To validate the deployment through successful UE registration and data connectivity
4. To provide a reference for researchers establishing 5G testbed environments

1.4 Report Structure

This report follows a systematic progression through three main phases: background and preparation (Sections 2-4), implementation and configuration (Sections 5-7), and validation and analysis (Sections 8-10). The journey begins with establishing theoretical foundations in 5G core

networking and reviewing related work (Section 2), followed by architectural overview (Section 3) and environment specification (Section 4). The implementation phase covers free5GC deployment (Section 5), UERANSIM configuration (Section 6), and simulation execution (Section 7). The final phase validates results (Section 8), documents troubleshooting solutions (Section 9), and concludes with insights and future directions (Section 10), complemented by resource acknowledgments (Section 11).

2 Background and Related Work

2.1 5G Core Network Architecture

The 5G Core (5GC) network, as specified by 3GPP in Release 15 and subsequent releases, adopts a Service-Based Architecture (SBA) that differs fundamentally from the point-to-point interfaces of previous generations. In SBA, Network Functions (NFs) expose their services through HTTP/2-based RESTful APIs, enabling flexible service discovery and consumption (3). The key Network Functions in the 5G core include:

- **Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF):** Handles registration, connection, and mobility management
- **Session Management Function (SMF):** Manages PDU sessions and UPF selection
- **User Plane Function (UPF):** Handles user data forwarding between RAN and data networks
- **Unified Data Management (UDM):** Manages subscriber data and authentication credentials
- **Authentication Server Function (AUSF):** Handles authentication procedures
- **Network Repository Function (NRF):** Provides service discovery functionality
- **Policy Control Function (PCF):** Provides policy rules for network behavior

2.2 Open-Source 5G Implementations

Several open-source projects have emerged to implement the 5G core network. free5GC, developed by the National Yang Ming Chiao Tung University (NYCU) in Taiwan, provides a complete implementation of 5G core NFs written in Go (2). Open5GS is another popular implementation written in C, supporting both 4G EPC and 5G core (4). OpenAirInterface (OAI) provides both RAN and core network implementations (5). Each project has different characteristics in terms of language, completeness, and community support.

2.3 UERANSIM

UERANSIM is an open-source 5G UE and RAN (gNodeB) simulator that implements 3GPP Release 15 specifications (6). It enables testing of 5G core networks without requiring physical radio equipment. UERANSIM supports essential procedures including registration, PDU session establishment, and data transfer, making it an ideal companion for testing open-source 5G core implementations.

3 System Architecture

3.1 Overall Architecture

The implemented system follows the 3GPP 5G system architecture with UERANSIM providing the UE and gNB simulation. Figure 1 illustrates the logical architecture showing the relationships between components.

Figure 1: Logical system architecture showing UERANSIM and free5GC components

3.2 Interface Definitions

Table 1 summarizes the key interfaces used in the deployment, following 3GPP specifications.

Table 1: 5G Network Interfaces

Interface	Connection	Protocol	Purpose
N1	UE – AMF	NAS	Registration, session mgmt
N2	gNB – AMF	SCTP/NGAP (Port 38412)	Control plane signaling
N3	gNB – UPF	GTP-U (Port 2152)	User plane data
N4	SMF – UPF	PCFP	Session rules, QoS
N6	UPF – DN	IP	External data network
SBI	NF – NF	HTTP/2 + JSON	Service-based interface

4 Implementation Environment

4.1 Hardware Configuration

The implementation was conducted on a virtualized environment with the specifications shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Virtual Machine Specifications

Component	Specification
Hypervisor	VirtualBox 7.2.4
Operating System	Ubuntu 20.04.6 LTS (64-bit)
Memory	4+ GB RAM (minimum 2 GB)
Storage	25+ GB
CPU	4 (minimum 2)
Network Adapter 1	NAT or Bridge Adapter (enp0s3) – External connectivity
Network Adapter 2	Host-only Adapter (enp0s8) – Internal network

4.2 Software Dependencies

Table 3 lists the software components and their versions used in this implementation.

Table 3: Software Dependencies

Software	Version	Purpose
Go	1.24.x	free5GC compilation
MongoDB	4.x	Subscriber database
gtp5g	Latest	Kernel module for GTP-U
CMake	3.16.3	UERANSIM build system
UERANSIM	3.2.7	UE and gNB simulation

4.3 Network Configuration

The network was configured with dual interfaces to provide both external connectivity and internal communication. Table 4 shows the IP address assignments used in this deployment.

Table 4: Network Configuration

Interface	IP Address	Purpose
enp0s3	172.20.10.12/28	Bridge adapter (external/NAT)
enp0s8	192.168.56.101/24	Host-only adapter (management)
AMF (N2)	127.0.0.18	NGAP interface to gNB
UPF (N3)	127.0.0.8	GTP-U interface to gNB
UE Pool	10.60.0.0/16	IP pool for UE PDU sessions

The host-only interface is configured manually. Table 5 shows the IP address assignments used in the Host-Only Interface deployment.

Table 5: Host-Only Network Configuration

Component	Configuration
Gateway IP	192.168.56.1
Subnet Mask	255.255.255.0
DHCP Range	192.168.56.3 – 192.168.56.254

5 Deployment Methodology

Run the following commands in the terminal to update and upgrade the Ubuntu VM, ensuring it has the latest security updates.

```
1 sudo apt update
2 sudo apt upgrade -y
3 sudo apt install net-tools vim -y
```

Listing 1: Update and upgrade the Ubuntu VM

5.1 Static Network Configuration

Configure static IPs using Netplan. By default, the Host-only network interface obtains its IP address through DHCP.

```
1 sudo vim /etc/netplan/00-installer-config.yaml
```

Listing 2: Configure static IPs using Netplan

Modify the yaml file with the following content:

```
1 network:
2   version: 2
```

```
3 ethernets:
4   enp0s3:
5     dhcp4: true
6   enp0s8:
7     dhcp4: false
8   addresses: [192.168.56.101/24]
```

Listing 3: Modify the yaml file

To edit, type 'i' (for insert mode), make your changes, then press Esc or ctrl+C, type ':wq!' and press Enter to save and quit.

After modifying the file, apply the settings with these commands.

```
1 sudo netplan try
2 sudo netplan apply
```

Listing 4: Apply Network Configuration

5.2 Kernel Compatibility Check

free5GC requires Linux kernel version 5.0.0-23-generic or 5.4.x. Verify your system compatibility:

```
1 uname -r
```

Listing 5: Kernel Compatibility Check

5.3 Essential Tools Installation

Install fundamental development and package management tools:

```
1 sudo apt -y install wget git
```

Listing 6: Essential Tools Installation

5.4 Go Programming Language Installation

5.4.1 Go 1.24.0 Installation

```
1 # Download Go 1.24.0 from mirror
2 wget https://dl.google.com/go/go1.24.0.linux-amd64.tar.gz
3
4 # Alternative source if primary mirror fails
5 wget https://go.dev/dl/go1.24.0.linux-amd64.tar.gz
```

Listing 7: Go 1.24.0 Installation

5.4.2 Go Environment Configuration

Configure the Go workspace and environment variables:

```
1 # Create Go workspace directory structure
2 mkdir -p ~/go/{bin, pkg, src}
3
4 echo 'export GOPATH=$HOME/go' >> ~/.bashrc
5 echo 'export GOROOT=/usr/local/go' >> ~/.bashrc
6 echo 'export PATH=$PATH:$GOPATH/bin:$GOROOT/bin' >> ~/.bashrc
7 echo 'export GOMODCACHE=$GOPATH/pkg/mod' >> ~/.bashrc
8
9 # Apply environment changes
10 source ~/.bashrc
11
12 # Verify successful installation
13 go version
14
15 Expected Output : go version go1.24.0 linux/amd64}
```

Listing 8: Go Environment Configuration

5.5 MongoDB Database Installation

5.5.1 CPU Feature Verification

Modern MongoDB requires AVX instruction set support. First, run this command to check if your CPU supports AVX.

```
1 lscpu | grep avx
```

Listing 9: CPU Feature Verification

5.5.2 MongoDB Repository Configuration

Add the official MongoDB repository and install MongoDB 7.0:

```
1 # Install prerequisite packages
2 sudo apt install -y gnupg curl
3
4 # Import MongoDB GPG key
5 curl -fsSL https://www.mongodb.org/static/pgp/server-7.0.asc | sudo
   gpg -o /usr/share/keyrings/mongodb-server-7.0.gpg --dearmor
6
7 # Add MongoDB repository to APT sources
```

```
8 echo "deb [ arch=amd64,arm64 signed-by=/usr/share/keyrings/mongodb-
  server-7.0.gpg ] https://repo.mongodb.org/apt/ubuntu focal/
  mongodb-org/7.0 multiverse" | sudo tee /etc/apt/sources.list.d/
  mongodb-org-7.0.list
9
10 # Update package list and install MongoDB
11 sudo apt update
12 sudo apt install -y mongodb-org
```

Listing 10: MongoDB Repository Configuration

5.5.3 MongoDB Service Management

Start and verify the MongoDB service:

```
1 # Start MongoDB service
2 sudo systemctl start mongod
3
4 # Check service status
5 sudo systemctl status mongod
```

Listing 11: MongoDB Service Management


```
● mongod.service - MongoDB Database Server
   Loaded: loaded (/lib/systemd/system/mongod.service; disabled; vendor pres
   Active: active (running) since Fri 2026-02-06 21:30:25 CST; 11s ago
     Docs: https://docs.mongodb.org/manual
    Main PID: 49432 (mongod)
      Memory: 70.8M
      CGroup: /system.slice/mongod.service
              └─49432 /usr/bin/mongod --config /etc/mongod.conf
```

Figure 2: Running Status of MongoDB

5.6 Build Dependencies Installation

Install compilation tools and libraries required for free5GC:

```
1 sudo apt -y update
2 sudo apt -y install git gcc g++ cmake autoconf libtool pkg-config
  libmnl-dev libyaml-dev apt-transport-https ca-certificates curl
  software-properties-common make
```

Listing 12: Build Dependency Installation

After completing these installations, VM now has the tools and dependencies needed to build and run free5GC.

```
g++ is already the newest version (4:9.3.0-1ubuntu2).
gcc is already the newest version (4:9.3.0-1ubuntu2).
libmnl-dev is already the newest version (1.0.4-2).
libtool is already the newest version (2.4.6-14).
libyaml-dev is already the newest version (0.2.2-1).
make is already the newest version (4.2.1-1.2).
pkg-config is already the newest version (0.29.1-0ubuntu4).
ca-certificates is already the newest version (20240203~20.04.1).
cmake is already the newest version (3.16.3-1ubuntu1.20.04.1).
curl is already the newest version (7.68.0-1ubuntu2.25).
git is already the newest version (1:2.25.1-1ubuntu3.14).
software-properties-common is already the newest version (0.99.9.12).
apt-transport-https is already the newest version (2.0.11).
```

Figure 3: Build Dependencies

5.7 free5GC Source Code Compilation

5.7.1 Repository Cloning

Clone free5GC version 4.1.0 with all submodules:

```
1 cd ~
2 git clone --recursive -b v4.1.0 -j `nproc` https://github.com/
  free5gc/free5gc.git
3 cd free5gc
```

Listing 13: free5GC Repository Cloning

5.7.2 Control Plane Network Functions Compilation

Build the core network functions:

```
1 # Build all control plane Network Functions
2 make
3
4 # Alternative: Build individual Network Functions
5 make amf
```

Listing 14: Network Functions Compilation

5.7.3 User Plane Function (UPF) Compilation

Build the data plane components:

```
1 # Install GTP5G kernel module
2 git clone -b v0.9.14 https://github.com/free5gc/gtp5g.git
3 cd gtp5g
4 make
```

```
5 sudo make install
6
7 # Build User Plane Function
8 cd ~/free5gc
9 make upf
```

Listing 15: User Plane Function Installation

5.8 Web Console Installation

5.8.1 Node.js Environment Setup

```
1 # Add Node.js repository and install
2 curl -fsSL https://deb.nodesource.com/setup_20.x | sudo -E bash -
3 sudo apt update
4 sudo apt install nodejs -y
5
6 # Enable Corepack
7 sudo corepack enable
```

Listing 16: Node.js Installation


```
All packages are up to date.
2026-02-07 00:15:12 - Repository configured successfully.
2026-02-07 00:15:12 - To install Node.js, run: apt install nodejs -y
2026-02-07 00:15:12 - You can use N|solid Runtime as a node.js alternative
2026-02-07 00:15:12 - To install N|solid Runtime, run: apt install nsolid -y
```

Figure 4: Node.js Environment Setup

5.8.2 Web Console Compilation

```
1 cd ~/free5gc
2 make webconsole
```

Listing 17: Web Console Build

5.9 Network Configuration

5.9.1 IP Forwarding Enablement

Essential for packet routing between network interfaces:

```
1 sudo sysctl -w net.ipv4.ip_forward=1
```

Listing 18: Enable IP Forwarding

5.9.2 Network Address Translation (NAT) Configuration

Configure MASQUERADE rule for external network connectivity:

```
1 # General command structure
2 sudo iptables -t nat -A POSTROUTING -o <dn_interface> -j MASQUERADE
3
4 # Example with interface enp0s3
5 sudo iptables -t nat -A POSTROUTING -o enp0s3 -j MASQUERADE
```

Listing 19: NAT Rule Configuration

5.9.3 Firewall Management (Optional)

Disable firewall to prevent connectivity issues:

```
1 sudo systemctl stop ufw
2 sudo systemctl disable ufw
```

Listing 20: Firewall Disablement

5.10 System Launch and Verification

5.11 free5GC Launch

```
1 cd ~/free5gc
2 ./run.sh
```

Listing 21: Start free5GC

5.12 Web Console Activation

```
1 cd ~/free5gc/webconsole
2 ./bin/webconsole
```

Listing 22: Start Web Console

5.13 Access Configuration

Open your web browser from your host machine, and connect to Webconsole

Access URL: `http://<VM_IP>:5000`

Example: `http://192.168.56.101:5000`

Default: Username: admin / Password: free5gc

Figure 5: Web Console Interface

6 UERANSIM Installation

6.1 VM Creation and Configuration

Create a new virtual machine for UERANSIM simulator by cloning from the base VM:

VM Configuration Requirements	
VM Name:	ueransim
Network MACs:	Generate new for all cards
Connectivity:	Internet + SSH
Hostname:	ueransim
Host-only IP:	192.168.56.102 (static)

6.2 Network Verification

After configuration, reboot both VMs and verify connectivity:

```
1 # From ueransim VM:
2 ping 192.168.56.101
3
4 # From free5gc VM:
5 ping 192.168.56.102
```

Listing 23: Network Connectivity Verification

6.3 Network Interface Configuration

6.3.1 Netplan Configuration

Configure static IP for the Host-only network interface:

```
1 sudo vim /etc/netplan/00-installer-config.yaml
```

Listing 24: Edit Network Configuration

Add the following configuration:

```
1 network:
2   version: 2
3   ethernets:
4     enp0s3:
5       dhcp4: true
6     enp0s8:
7       dhcp4: false
8     addresses: [192.168.56.102/24]
```

Listing 25: Netplan Configuration File

6.4 Apply Network Settings

```
1 sudo netplan try
2 sudo netplan apply
```

Listing 26: Apply Network Configuration

6.5 UERANSIM Installation

6.5.1 Repository Cloning

Clone the UERANSIM repository and select appropriate version:

```
1 cd ~
2 git clone https://github.com/aligungr/UERANSIM
3 cd UERANSIM
```

Listing 27: Clone UERANSIM Repository

Select the appropriate branch based on your free5GC version:

- **free5GC v3.3.0 or below:** `git checkout 3a96298`
- **free5GC v3.4.0 or above:** `git checkout e4c492d`
- **free5GC v3.4.x with EAP-AKA-PRIME fix:** `git checkout 85a0fbf`

6.6 System Updates and Dependencies

Install required system packages and tools:

```
1 # Update system packages
2 sudo apt update
3 sudo apt upgrade
4
5 # Install required tools
6 sudo apt install make g++ libsctp-dev lksctp-tools iproute2
7 sudo snap install cmake --classic
```

Listing 28: Install Dependencies

6.7 Build UERANSIM

Compile the UERANSIM simulator:

```
1 cd ~/UERANSIM
2 make
```

Listing 29: Build UERANSIM


```
cp cmake-build-release/nr-gnb build/
cp cmake-build-release/nr-ue build/
cp cmake-build-release/nr-cli build/
cp cmake-build-release/libdevbnd.so build/
cp tools/nr-binder build/
UERANSIM successfully built.
desh@desh-VirtualBox:~/UERANSIM$
```

Figure 6: Build UERANSIM

6.8 Setting free5GC and UERANSIM Parameters

Update the following files to use the host-only IP:

AMF

```
1 cd ~/free5gc
2 # AMF
3 nano config/amfcfg.yaml -> ngapIpList: 192.168.56.101
4
5 # SMF
6 nano config/smfcfg.yaml -> endpoints: 192.168.56.101
7
8 # UPF
9 nano config/upfcfg.yaml -> addr: 192.168.56.101
```

Listing 30: Update Configuration Files with Host-Only IP Address

6.9 Verification

Confirm connectivity:

```
# free5gc VM
ping 192.168.56.101

#UERANSIM VM
ping 192.168.56.102
```

Listing 31: Network Connectivity Verification Commands

Once all services are running, the UERANSIM UE can successfully register to the free5GC core and establish data sessions.

6.10 UERANSIM gNB Configuration

The gNB configuration (`free5gc-gnb.yaml`) must be aligned with the free5GC AMF configuration:

```
1 mcc: '208'
2 mnc: '93'
3 nci: '0x000000010'
4 idLength: 32
5 tac: 1
6
7 linkIp: 127.0.0.1
8 ngapIp: 127.0.0.1
9 gtpIp: 127.0.0.1
10
11 amfConfigs:
12   - address: 127.0.0.18
13     port: 38412
14
15 slices:
16   - sst: 1
17     sd: 0x010203
18
19 ignoreStreamIds: true
```

Listing 32: gNB Configuration (`free5gc-gnb.yaml`)

6.11 UERANSIM UE Configuration

The UE configuration must match the subscriber data registered in the free5GC database:

```
1 supi: 'imsi-208930000000001'
2 mcc: '208'
3 mnc: '93'
4
5 key: '8baf473f2f8fd09487cccbd7097c6862'
6 op: '8e27b6af0e692e750f32667a3b14605d'
7 opType: 'OPC'
8 amf: '8000'
9
10 gnbSearchList:
11   - 127.0.0.1
12
13 sessions:
14   - type: 'IPv4'
15     apn: 'internet'
16     slice:
17       sst: 1
18       sd: 0x010203
19
20 configured-nssai:
21   - sst: 1
22     sd: 0x010203
23
24 default-nssai:
25   - sst: 1
26     sd: 0x010203
```

Listing 33: UE Configuration (free5gc-ue.yaml)

7 Subscriber Registration & Simulation Execution

7.1 Start Webconsole

```
1 cd ~/free5gc/webconsole
2 ./bin/webconsole
```

Listing 34: Start Webconsole

Access: <http://localhost:5000> or <http://192.168.56.101:5000>

Default Credentials: Username: admin, Password: free5gc

7.2 Add Subscriber

Navigate to **Subscribers > New Subscriber**. Enter these values (must match UE config):

Parameter	Value
IMSI	208930000000001
K (Key)	8baf473f2f8fd09487cccbd7097c6862
OPC	8e27b6af0e692e750f32667a3b14605d
SST / SD	1 / 010203
DNN	internet

Table 6: Subscriber Configuration Parameters

7.3 Running the Simulation

NOTE: Components must start in order: **MongoDB > free5GC > Webconsole > gNB > UE**

7.3.1 Terminal 1: Start free5GC Core

```
1 cd ~/free5gc
2 ./run.sh
```

Listing 35: Start free5GC Core

7.3.2 Terminal 2: Start Webconsole (optional)

```
1 cd ~/free5gc/webconsole
2 ./bin/webconsole
```

Listing 36: Start Webconsole

7.3.3 Terminal 3: Start gNB

```
1 cd ~/UERANSIM
2 ./build/nr-gnb -c config/free5gc-gnb.yaml
```

Listing 37: Start gNB

Expected output:

```
1 [sctp] [info] SCTP connection established (127.0.0.18:38412)
2 [ngap] [info] NG Setup procedure is successful
```

7.4 Terminal 4: Start UE (with sudo)

```
1 cd ~/UERANSIM
2 sudo ./build/nr-ue -c config/free5gc-ue.yaml
```

Listing 38: Start UE

Expected output:

```
1 [nas] [info] Initial Registration is successful
2 [nas] [info] PDU Session establishment is successful PSI[1]
3 [app] [info] Connection setup for PDU session[1] is successful,
4             TUN interface[uesimtun0, 10.60.0.2] is up.
```

7.5 Verification

After successful setup, verify the connection:

```
1 # Check UE IP address
2 ip addr show uesimtun0
3
4 # Ping test
5 ping -I uesimtun0 8.8.8.8
6
7 # Check PDU sessions
8 curl http://localhost:5000/api/subscriber/208930000000001
```

Listing 39: Verification

7.5.1 Troubleshooting Tips

- Ensure MongoDB is running: `sudo systemctl status mongod`
- Check if ports are available: `netstat -tulpn | grep -E '(5000|8080|38412)'`
- Verify UE configuration matches webconsole subscriber data
- Check firewall settings: `sudo ufw status`
- View detailed logs: `tail -f /free5gc/log/*.log`

8 Results and Discussion

8.1 Deployment Results

The deployment was successfully completed with all components operational. Table 7 summarizes the validation results.

Table 7: Deployment Validation Results

Test Case	Expected Result	Status
free5GC NF Startup	All NFs running	✓PASS
gNB-AMF SCTP Connection	NG Setup success	✓PASS
UE Initial Registration	Registration accepted	✓PASS
PDU Session Establishment	Session established	✓PASS
TUN Interface Creation	uesimtun0 up	✓PASS
Data Plane Connectivity	Ping successful	✓PASS

8.2 Discussion

The successful deployment demonstrates the viability of using free5GC and UERANSIM for 5G research and education. The combination provides a complete end-to-end 5G system simulation without requiring physical radio equipment or expensive infrastructure.

The challenges encountered during deployment highlight areas where improved documentation and error handling could benefit users. In particular, the dependency version requirements and permission requirements for network interface creation are common sources of confusion for new users.

The use of loopback addresses for NF communication, while suitable for single-machine deployments, may require modification for distributed deployments across multiple hosts. Future work could explore container-based deployment using Docker or Kubernetes for improved isolation and scalability.

9 Comprehensive Troubleshooting Guide

This section documents all challenges encountered during the free5GC implementation process along with their respective solutions. The troubleshooting guide is organized by error type for quick reference.

9.1 System Configuration Issues

9.1.1 Netplan Configuration Syntax Error

Problem: Error message “unknown key ‘enp0s8’” when applying netplan configuration.

Cause: YAML indentation error causing interface definitions to be nested incorrectly.

Solution: Ensure proper YAML structure with correct indentation (use spaces, not tabs):

```
# Correct structure:
network:
  version: 2
  ethernets:
    enp0s3:
      dhcp4: no
    enp0s8:
      dhcp4: false
      addresses: [192.168.56.101/24]
```

Listing 40: Solution for Netplan Configuration Syntax Error

9.1.2 Disk Space Exhaustion

Problem: “No space left on device” error during compilation or operation.

Cause: Virtual machine or Live USB running out of storage.

Solutions:

1. Immediate cleanup:

```
# Check disk usage
df -h

# Clean apt cache
sudo apt clean
sudo apt autoremove -y
```

Listing 41: Immediate cleanup

2. Recover broken installations:

```
sudo dpkg --configure -a
```

Listing 42: Recover broken installations

3. Expand the VirtualBox hard disk

4. **Critical:** If using Live server, install Ubuntu to hard disk.

9.1.3 Read-Only Filesystem

Problem: “Cannot create file: Read-only file system”

Cause: Filesystem mounted as read-only, often in Live USB mode.

Solution:

```
# Remount as read-write
sudo mount -o remount,rw /
# If persistent, install Ubuntu properly
```

Listing 43: Solution for Read-Only Filesystem

9.2 Dependency and Build Issues

9.2.1 CMake Version Incompatibility

Problem: UERANSIM build fails with “CMake 3.17 or higher is required. You are running version 3.16.3”

Solutions:

1. Remove old CMake and install via snap:

```
sudo apt remove cmake -y
sudo snap install cmake --classic
```

Listing 44: Remove old CMake and install via snap

2. Update PATH for snap installation:

```
export PATH=$PATH:/snap/bin
# Or permanently add to ~/.bashrc:
echo 'export PATH=$PATH:/snap/bin' >> ~/.bashrc
```

Listing 45: Update PATH for snap installation

3. Refresh shell cache:

```
hash -r
```

Listing 46: Refresh shell cache

9.2.2 Go Installation Issues

Problem: free5GC requires Go 1.24+ but installation fails or times out.

Solutions:

1. **Download from Chinese mirror:** (If you are accessing from China with VPN)

```
wget https://golang.google.cn/dl/go1.24.0.linux-amd64.tar.gz
```

Listing 47: Solution for Go Installation Issues

2. **Clean installation:**

```
# Remove old installation
sudo rm -rf /usr/local/go

# Extract new version
sudo tar -C /usr/local -xzf go1.24.0.linux-amd64.tar.gz

# Update PATH
echo 'export PATH=$PATH:/usr/local/go/bin' >> ~/.bashrc
source ~/.bashrc

# Verify
go version # Should show: go version go1.24.0 linux/amd64
```

Listing 48: Clean installation

3. **Set Go proxy for China:**

```
export GOPROXY=https://goproxy.cn,direct
# Or alternative:
export GOPROXY=https://goproxy.io,direct
```

Listing 49: Set Go proxy for China

9.2.3 CPU Compatibility (AVX Support)

Problem: Certain features may require AVX instructions.

Check:

```
grep avx /proc/cpuinfo
```

Listing 50: CPU Compatibility Check

Note: Most modern CPUs support AVX. If not available, consider using a different machine or virtualization with AVX emulation.

9.3 Network and Connection Issues

9.3.1 SCTP Connection Refused

Problem: “SCTP could not connect: Connection refused”

Causes and Solutions:

- **AMF not running:**

```
# Verify AMF is listening
ss -tlnp | grep 38412

# If empty, start free5GC core first
cd ~/free5gc && ./run.sh
```

Listing 51: Solution for SCTP Connection Refused

- **Firewall blocking:**

```
sudo ufw allow 38412/tcp
sudo ufw allow 38412/udp
```

Listing 52: Firewall blocking

9.3.2 MongoDB Connection Refused

Problem: “dial tcp 127.0.0.1:27017: connect: connection refused”

Solution:

```
# Start MongoDB service
sudo systemctl start mongod
sudo systemctl enable mongod
sudo systemctl status mongod

# Verify connection
mongosh --eval "db.runCommand({connectionStatus: 1})"
```

Listing 53: Solution for MongoDB Connection Refused

9.3.3 NRF Registration Failed

Problem: “Webconsole-AF register to NRF Error - connection refused”

Solution: Ensure proper startup sequence:

1. Start free5GC core (./run.sh)
2. Wait for all NF registrations (check logs)
3. Start webconsole

9.4 Port and Process Conflicts

9.4.1 Port Already in Use

Problem: “bind: address already in use” on ports 5000, 2121, or 38412.

Solutions:

1. Kill specific processes:

```
# Kill by port
sudo kill $(sudo lsof -t -i:5000)
sudo kill $(sudo lsof -t -i:2121)
sudo kill $(sudo lsof -t -i:38412)
```

Listing 54: Kill specific processes

2. Kill all free5GC processes:

```
sudo pkill -f free5gc
sudo killall -9 webconsole
sudo killall -9 nr-ue
sudo killall -9 nr-gnb
```

Listing 55: Kill all free5GC processes

3. Verify ports are free:

```
ss -tlnp | grep -E "5000|2121|38412"
# Should show nothing if ports are free
```

Listing 56: Verify ports are free

9.5 Permission and Access Issues

9.5.1 TUN Interface Permission Denied

Problem: “TUN interface could not be setup. Permission denied.”

Cause: TUN/TAP interface creation requires root privileges.

Solution:

```
sudo ./build/nr-ue -c config/free5gc-ue.yaml
```

Listing 57: Solution for TUN Interface Permission Denied

9.6 Summary Table

Table 8 provides a quick reference for all common issues and solutions.

Table 8: Comprehensive Troubleshooting Reference

Issue	Solution
Netplan YAML syntax error	Fix indentation; use spaces not tabs
CMake version too old	Remove apt version, install via snap
CMake not found after snap	Update PATH: <code>export PATH=\$PATH:/snap/bin</code>
Disk space full	Clean apt cache, expand virtual disk
Go installation timeout	Use Chinese mirror, set GOPROXY
SCTP connection refused	Start free5GC core first, check AMF
MongoDB connection refused	Start service: <code>sudo systemctl start mongod</code>
Port already in use	Kill processes: <code>sudo pkill -f free5gc</code>
TUN interface permission denied	Run UE with sudo
Read-only filesystem	Remount RW or install Ubuntu properly
NRF registration failed	Follow correct startup sequence

9.7 Best Practices for Prevention

1. **Startup Sequence:** Always follow: MongoDB → free5GC → Webconsole → gNB → UE

2. **Disk Space Management:** Regularly clean cache and monitor disk usage
3. **Process Management:** Use scripts for consistent start/stop procedures
4. **Network Configuration:** Test network connectivity before starting components

This comprehensive troubleshooting guide covers all major issues encountered during free5GC deployment. Following these solutions will ensure a stable 5G core network simulation environment.

10 Conclusion and Future Work

10.1 Conclusion

This technical report has presented a comprehensive guide for deploying an open-source 5G core network using free5GC and UERANSIM. The deployment was successfully completed on Ubuntu 20.04 LTS, achieving full end-to-end connectivity from simulated UE through the 5G core to external data networks.

Key contributions of this work include:

1. Detailed documentation of the deployment procedure with specific configuration parameters
2. Identification and resolution of common implementation challenges
3. Validation of the deployment through testing

The documented methodology provides a reproducible approach for researchers, students, and practitioners seeking to establish 5G testbed environments for education and research purposes.

10.2 Future Work

Several directions for future work are identified:

1. Container-based deployment using Docker/Kubernetes for improved portability and scalability
2. Performance benchmarking and optimization of the 5G core under various load conditions
3. Integration with network slicing configurations for multi-tenant scenarios
4. Exploration of edge computing scenarios with Multiple Access Edge Computing (MEC)
5. Comparison with other open-source 5G implementations (Open5GS, OAI)

11 Acknowledgments and Resources

This implementation was made possible by the open-source contributions of the free5GC Team and educational resources from the Linux Foundation. The following resources were instrumental in this project:

11.1 Official Resources

- **free5GC Official Website:** <https://www.free5gc.org> - Primary source for software, documentation, and updates
- **free5GC GitHub Repository:** <https://github.com/free5gc/free5gc> - Source code and issue tracking
- **UERANSIM GitHub:** <https://github.com/aligungr/UERANSIM> - 5G NSA and SA RAN simulator

11.2 Educational Resources

- **Linux Foundation Course:** "Introduction to free5GC (LFS114)" - Comprehensive training covering installation, configuration, and operation
- **Course Link:** <https://training.linuxfoundation.org/training/introduction-to-free5gc-lfs114/>
- **Course Code:** LFS114

References

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- [7] Linux Foundation, “Introduction to free5GC (LFS114),” Linux Foundation Training, 2024.